
Matrix Metalloproteinase-8 as Serum Biochemical Marker Accurately Predict Liver Fibrosis in Hepatitis C Patients

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Abstract Objective: Liver biopsy is the gold standard for assessing hepatitis C virus (HCV)-related fibrosis, but it is invasive and prone to complications. Aim. Our aim was to study and validate the performance of MMP-8 as simple blood marker of liver fibrosis in HCV patients in addition to GSH and NO. Patients and methods: A total of 75 Egyptian patients with clinically and laboratory confirmed hepatitis C patients (HCV) and liver fibrosis were included in the present study. They were recruited from the Internal Medicine Department, EL Ahrar Hospital, Zagazig, Egypt that approved the present study. Result: NO values were significantly increased gradually according to the progression of fibrosis degree (F1, F2, F3 and F4) compared to healthy control individuals (F0). Also, GST activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis till F4 compared to healthy control individuals (F0). Meanwhile, GST activity was reduced in F4 compared to other fibrotic degrees (F1, F2, and F3). On the other hand, MMP-8 activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis compared to healthy control individuals (F0). Conclusion: using of matrix metalloproteinase-8 a simple biochemical marker which accurately predicts different stages of liver fibrosis in patients with chronic HCV infection, and may substantially reduce the necessity for liver biopsy.

Keywords Metalloproteinase-8, Biochemical Marker, Hepatitis C

Introduction

HCV and its long-term resultant consequences, is a major endemic medical health problem in Egypt [1]. In the Nile Delta and Upper Egypt, infection rates can be much higher at around 26% and 28%, respectively [2]. Chronic hepatitis C virus infection is important globally as a cause of liver-related morbidity and mortality with hepatic fibrosis, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma as the major clinical sequelae [3]. Liver fibrosis is a significant health problem, with a worldwide mortality attributable to cirrhosis and primary liver cancer of around 1.5 million deaths per year [4]. In patients with chronic viral hepatitis, precise definition of the hepatic fibrosis stage is the most important parameter to assess the risk of disease progression and to decide for an immediate and appropriate antiviral therapy. In these patients liver biopsy represents the gold standard for valuating the presence, type and stage of liver fibrosis [5]. This procedure, however, is invasive, stressful for patients, costly, and difficult to standardize [6, 7].

Collagenase-2 (MMP-8), a member of the MMP family which has recently emerged as a candidate to play a protective role during tumor progression. MMP-8 is mainly produced by neutrophils, and it has been implicated in a

variety of tissue remodeling processes associated with inflammatory conditions [8]. Oxidative stress is a state of imbalance between the production and dismutation, or detoxification, of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by cellular mechanisms that can significantly affect signal transduction, gene expression, and functional responses of involved cells or cause cell damage. Evidence of oxidative stress has been detected in almost all the clinical and experimental conditions of chronic liver diseases with different etiology and fibrosis progression rate, and oxidative stress has been proposed as a major pro-fibrogenic mechanism [9,10]. Cellular glutathione (GSH) and related enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), glutathione S-transferase (GST) and glutathione reductase (GR) are among the principal protective mechanisms against endogenous and exogenous toxic substances and free radicals-mediated damage in liver tissue as well as in other tissues [11,12]. On the one hand, NO is important in the resolution of some viral infections; on the other hand, it could cause or potentiate deleterious effects on the host. Thus, advances in our knowledge of the role of NO in immunomodulation and in the pathogenesis of viral diseases could contribute to the development of vaccines and therapeutic strategies [13,14].

Patients and Methods

A total of 75 Egyptian patients with clinically and laboratory confirmed chronic hepatitis C (CHC) and liver fibrosis were included in the present study. They were recruited from the Internal Medicine Department, EL Ahrar Hospital, Zagazig, Egypt that approved the present study. An informed consent was obtained from each individual participated in the present study and all were fully informed concerning the nature of the disease and the diagnostic procedures involved. The HCV infection and liver fibrosis were diagnosed based on biochemical, serologic and histological criteria. In addition to 15 samples from healthy volunteers (negative control) were used.

Liver biopsy

Needle liver biopsy specimens ($n = 75$) were taken from the patients and examined by a pathologist unaware of the laboratory results. Biopsies were processed for diagnostic purposes, fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin, cut into 4 μm thick and routinely stained with hematoxyline and eosin stain. Fibrosis was assessed according to the Metavir scoring system on a five-point scale (F0 = no fibrosis, F1 = portal fibrosis without septa, F2 = few septa, F3 = numerous septa without cirrhosis and F4 = cirrhosis). Activity grading by the Metavir system (based on the intensity of periportal and lobular necro-inflammation) was scored as follows: A0 = no histological activity, A1 = mild activity, A2 = moderate activity and A3 = severe activity. The presence of stage F2, F3 or F4 was termed 'significant fibrosis', whereas the term 'advanced fibrosis' was reserved for stage F3 or F4. The presence of stage F4 was termed 'liver cirrhosis' [15].

Blood samples

Blood samples were collected from all healthy and patients by vein-puncture within 2 weeks of liver biopsy. Sera were separated from the blood samples and tested fresh for the tested biochemical marker matrix metalloproteinase-8 by the quantitative sandwich enzyme immunoassay technique according to Monaghan *et al.* [16], in addition to glutathione s-transferase activity by using Biodiagnostic kit method (Biodiagnostic company, Dokki, Giza, Egypt), according to the method of Habig *et al.* [17] and nitric oxide (NO) level was determined by using Biodiagnostic kit method (Biodiagnostic company, Dokki, Giza, Egypt), according to the method of Montgomery and Dymock [18].

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were done by a statistical software package (Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 15.0) for Microsoft Windows, SPSS Inc.). Descriptive results were expressed as mean \pm SD and range or number (percentage) of patients with a condition. Differences in continuous variables were assessed using Student's t-test or analysis of variance (ANOVA) and X^2 test for categorical variables [19].

Results

Diagnosis of samples

The present study involved 75 patients with clinically and laboratory confirmed chronic hepatitis C and liver fibrosis in addition to 15 negative controls (healthy volunteers). Positive patients with liver fibrosis were divided into different degrees according to METAVIR system as: 22 patients were categorized as F1 by (29%), 26 were F2 by (35%), 9 were F3 by (12%), and 18 patients were F4 by (24%).

The mean values of NO, GST and MMP-8 levels in healthy control individuals (F0) were found to be 17.91 ± 1.15 ($\mu\text{mol/l}$), 27.24 ± 3.2 (U/L) and 85.59 ± 9.27 (pg/ml) respectively. NO values were significantly increased gradually according to the progression of fibrosis degree to be 26.16 ± 2.8 , 55.41 ± 7.8 , 93.30 ± 4.6 , 93.34 ± 10.23 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 46.06%, 209.55%, 420.94% and 421.16%; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0). While, there was no significant difference between F3 and F4 stages, (Fig. 1). Also, GST activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis till F4, to be 169.43 ± 20.69 , 394.43 ± 51.95 , 565.44 ± 47.90 , and 224.88 ± 22.76 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 521.98%, 1347.98%, 1975.77%, and 725.55; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0). Meanwhile, GST activity was reduced in F4 compared to other fibrotic degrees (F1, F2, and F3), (Fig.2). On the other hand, MMP-8 activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis, to be 279.38 ± 27.13 , 454.75 ± 28.58 , 544.55 ± 25.11 and 846.11 ± 130.3 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 226.44%, 431.31%, 536.23% and 885.56%; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0), illustrated in (Fig.3).

Figure 1: NO levels in all studied groups

Figure 2: GST activity in all studied groups

Figure 3: MMP-8 activity in all studied groups

Correlations between different studied parameters among studied groups:

There were significant positive correlations between NO, GST and MMP-8 to each other according to the degree of liver fibrosis (Table 1) and (fig. 4).

Table 1: Pearson's correlations analysis between different studied parameters in patients studied groups:

Parameter		NO	GST	MMP-8
NO	r	-----	0.639**	0.898**
GST	r	0.639**	-----	0.465**
MMP-8	r	0.898**	0.465**	-----

**Correlation is significant at $p < 0.001$

Figure 4: Correlations between different parameters in all studied groups

The laboratory data of liver fibrosis and non liver fibrosis, advanced liver fibrosis and liver cirrhosis

In the present study, patients with significant fibrosis were associated with higher mean NO, GST and MMP-8 than those of non significant liver fibrosis with extremely significant difference ($p < 0.0001$; table 2). Patients with advanced liver fibrosis were associated with higher mean NO, GST and MMP-8 than those of non advanced liver fibrosis with extremely significant difference ($p < 0.0001$; table 3). Also, patients with liver cirrhosis were associated with higher mean NO, GST and MMP-8 than those of non liver cirrhosis with extremely significant difference ($p < 0.0001$; table 4).

Table 2: Levels of liver fibrosis markers in significant liver fibrosis and non significant liver fibrosis

Marker	Significant N=53	Non significant N=37	P value
NO($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	56.9 \pm 35.5	17.9 \pm 1.2	< 0.0001
GST (U/l)	343.8 \pm 123.4	111.1 \pm 72.5	< 0.0001
MMP-8 (pg/ml)	529.3 \pm 287.8	85.1 \pm 9.3	< 0.0001

Table 3: Levels of liver fibrosis markers in advanced liver fibrosis and non advanced liver fibrosis

Marker	Advanced N=27	Non advanced N=63	P value
NO($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	82.1 \pm 28.6	23.2 \pm 13.9	< 0.0001
GST (U/l)	338.4 \pm 166.8	209.8 \pm 134.3	< 0.0001
MMP-8 (pg/ml)	745 \pm 179	175.8 \pm 162	< 0.0001

Table 4: Levels of liver cirrhosis markers in liver cirrhosis and non liver cirrhosis

Marker	cirrhosis N=18	Non cirrhosis N=72	P value
NO($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	93.3 \pm 10.2	27.2 \pm 22.1	< 0.0001
GST (U/l)	224.8 \pm 22.7	254.3 \pm 173	< 0.0001
MMP-8 (pg/ml)	846.1 \pm 130	221.8 \pm 195.4	< 0.0001

Discussion

Clinical management of chronic hepatitis C is dependent on the extent of liver fibrosis. Liver biopsy, the gold standard, is still recommended in the majority of patients [20]. However, liver biopsy is invasive, requires an experienced gastroenterologist, examination is required by a professional histopathologist, adds expense and is associated with complications and mortality patients with chronic hepatitis C [21,22]. Biomarkers are being developed as alternatives to liver biopsy for predicting liver fibrosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C [23].

In the present study, nitric oxide (NO), glutathione s-transferase (GST) and matrix metalloproteinase-8 (MMP-8) were measured using standard methodologies in 75 patients with clinically and laboratory confirmed chronic hepatitis C and liver fibrosis in addition to 15 negative controls (healthy volunteers). The mean NO, GST and MMP-8 levels in healthy control individuals (F0) were found to be 17.91 ± 1.15 ($\mu\text{mol/l}$), 27.24 ± 3.2 (U/L) and 85.59 ± 9.27 (pg/ml) respectively. Nitric oxide (NO) values were significantly increased gradually according to the progression of fibrosis degree to be 26.16 ± 2.8 , 55.41 ± 7.8 , 93.30 ± 4.6 , 93.34 ± 10.23 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 46.06%, 209.55%, 420.94% and 421.16%; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0). While, there was no significant difference between F3 and F4 stages. Hepatic fibrosis in patients chronically infected with hepatitis B and C also appears to be correlated with increased expression of iNOS. Although the molecular mechanisms have not been well elucidated, it was shown that fibrosis levels were correlated positively with iNOS expression, as well as that of TGF- β , which is an oxidative stress inducer and profibrogenic cytokine [24]. There is a controversy regarding the production of NO in chronic HCV patients with studies reporting an increase [25,26], a decrease [27], or no change [28,29] in its level.

During this study, Glutathione s-transferase (GST) activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis till F4, to be 169.43 ± 20.69 , 394.43 ± 51.95 , 565.44 ± 47.90 , and 224.88 ± 22.76 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 521.98%, 1347.98%, 1975.77%, and 725.55; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0). Meanwhile, GST activity was reduced in F4 compared to other fibrotic degrees (F1, F2, and F3). An increased GSH level in chronic liver diseases has been reported in many reports [30,31]. GST is a sensitive marker in the diagnosis of alcoholic liver disease [32] as well a reliable marker in monitoring the response to chronic liver disease treatment [33]. In both clinical and experimental HCC, reduced global activity of GST has been observed within tumors [11], and the specific isoforms GST π 1 and GST α 1 [34,35] have been shown to be over expressed and have been used as biomarkers in experimental models of HCC.

In the current study, Matrix metalloproteinase-8 (MMP-8) activity was extremely significant elevated gradually with the degree of liver fibrosis, to be 279.38 ± 27.13 , 454.75 ± 28.58 , 544.55 ± 25.11 and 846.11 ± 130.3 in F1, F2, F3, and F4 by 226.44%, 431.31%, 536.23% and 885.56%; respectively; ($p < 0.001$), compared to healthy control individuals (F0). MMP-8, a member of the MMP family which has recently emerged as a candidate to play a protective role during tumor progression. MMP-8 is mainly produced by neutrophils, and it has been implicated in a variety of tissue remodeling processes associated with inflammatory conditions [8]. The predominant role of matrix metalloproteinase 8 in extracellular matrix turnover, modulation of inflammatory responses and other physiological processes is well documented. Several recent studies highlight the involvement of MMP8 in a wide range of pathologies and as a disease marker in some inflammatory disorders and in cancer progression [36]. Under physiological condition, inactive MMP-8 is expressed at low levels in tissues and body fluids, but its level and activation increase significantly under various pathological conditions, e.g., inflammatory, fibrosis diseases and cancers [37,38].

From this study we conclude the following:

Matrix metalloproteinase-8 (MMP-8) can be used as a potential biomarker for the diagnosis of liver fibrosis. It was shown that fibrosis levels were correlated positively with Nitric oxide (NO) concentration. Glutathione s-transferase (GST) activity was a reliable monitoring the response to chronic liver disease treatment. Addition of (NO) and (GST) to (MMP-8) gives a significant improvement in detection of different stages of fibrosis in patients with HCV. Therefore, combination of multiple markers may be more valuable in the diagnosis of liver fibrosis. Finally, There were significant positive correlations between NO levels, activity of GST with MMP-8 to each other according to the degree of liver fibrosis.

We can recommended that, using of matrix metalloproteinase-8 a simple and non-invasive biochemical marker for the assessment of different stages of hepatic fibrosis as alternatives to liver biopsy which is invasive, expensive, painful and in some settings impossible to do in patients with chronic HCV infection in addition of glutathione s-transferase activity and level of nitric oxide.

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